

MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE IS AN OUTSTANDING UZBEK POET

Hasanov Sirojiddin Nizomiddin o'g'li
talaba, Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
sirojiddinhasanov0@gmail.com

Annotation: An artist is a genius who raises the literature of every nation to the highest peaks. These are the incomparable works of genius, they have created immortal works still introduce to the world the intellect of the people to whom they belong, illuminating the minds of all mankind and giving strength and power to their hearts and minds. All of these have been brightened by this article.

Key words: literary criticism, literary process, talented scientist, historical period, ideological and artistic features of the epic

Annotatsiya: Har bir xalq adabiyotini eng yugori cho'qqilarga ko'taradigan dahlo san'atkorlari bo'ladi. Bu dahlo zotlar ro'yobga chigargan bemisl ishlar, ular yaratgan o'lmas asarlar hamon o'zlari mansub bo'lgan xalqning zakovatini dunyoga tanitib, butun insoniyatning ongini yoritib, qalbi va tafakkuriga kuch-quvvat, qudrat bag'ishlab kelmoqda. Bularning barchasi ushbu maqolada yoritilgan.

Kalitso'zlar: adabiy tanqid, adabiv iarayon, iste'dodli olim, tarixiy davr, eposning g'oyaviy va badiy xususiyatlari.

Maksud Shaikhzade was not only a mature artist, but also a well-educated researcher. His services in the field of literature are incomparable. From 1935 to 1938 he worked as a researcher at the Institute of Language and Literature, from 1938 to the end of his life as an associate professor, head of the department of "History of Uzbek classical literature" at the Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami. Over the years, Maksud Shaikhzade has created deep and serious scientific research as well as creative work. He taught the secrets of literature to many students. From the point of view of the great scholar, literary criticism is an issue in the history of literature. Maksud Shaikhzade studied in detail the period of Uzbek literature from folklore to modern literature, the issues of literary process, types and genres, art.

The works of the talented scientist devoted to the study of classical literature, in particular, the creative heritage of Alisher Navoi, have not lost their

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value. They are distinguished by their scientific nature, which gives us a wide range of information and teaches us research methods.

First of all, let's focus on Maksud Shaikhzade 's research on folklore and think about his folklore activity.

Maksud Shaikhzade studied the folklore in detail. In 1941, Fozil Yuldosh prepared for publication the epic "Sweet and Sugar" written by his son.

In addition to preparing this epic for publication, the scholar also wrote a large preface to it. The article at the beginning of the preface introduces a detailed analysis of the ideological and artistic features of the epic, its images in all respects. Until then, the absolute negative image gives a new interpretation to the character as stamped.

Maksud Shaikhzade rightly noted that a special study of Oriental mythology, including folk mythology, which is an artistic treasure of Uzbek folklore, requires a great deal of time and scientific training. Interestingly, for many years the image of the giant has not been interpreted in our folklore. The function of the image of the giant is still perceived by many as a negative, a symbol of evil. For the first time, Maksud Shaikhzade boldly said that this image should be evaluated according to the direction of events in each work, that giants are often interpreted as a powerful helper to mankind, revealing the secrets of intricate magic that is not an evil enemy of man. proved his point with characteristic evidence taken from his epics. In addition, he emphasizes one of the features of the epic "Sweet and Sugar". "... this epic in our hands is a certain legend. In fact, this epic is a bit enlightening for historians and ethnographers. and ethnographic information. By reading this epic, the reader will be able to learn the techniques of the old wars, the pre war Uzbek wrestlers, the defeated armies, as in our time, without surrendering the swords.

He knew what he had taken, the materials about the origins of the chase, the methods of punishment of the former feudal lords / his absolute death after the executioners had tied him to the hands of sinners, and by examining some more traditions, interesting scientific and spiritual features. After all, a good, beautiful, artistic epic can not be different. No matter how imaginary, mythical, it is a real of a certain historical period. it's natural to absorb the lines. "

It is known that the works of folklore are passed from language to language, from generation to generation. As a result, these works undergo various changes,

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some of the places that are unique to certain historical conditions fall, new events and views enter. Consequently, we see that in the works of some folk oral creations, especially in epics and fairy tales, events, customs, thoughts and views related to different historical conditions are reflected.

Alpomish is one of them. We see that Alpomish, which is popular both in content and form, has mastered the rules, forms and methods of poetry in the oral poetry of the people.

Therefore, it is impossible for a researcher interested in the history of literature to think deeply about the development of the literary process, forms and methods, fine arts, without coming to a definite idea and conclusions about this great artistic heritage.

In 1956, Maksud Shaikhzade conducted research on some poetic features of the epic "Alpomish", which provides extensive information about the weight, art, ideological and artistic features, content, the world of images of the epic. In particular, he notes that the rhythmic basis of the epic Alpomish is a syllabic system ("hijo weight or finger weight"), a weight that has been a characteristic feature of the oral poetry of all Turkic-speaking peoples. In addition, Maksud Shaikhzade pays special attention to the poetic features of the epic: saj, rhyme, radif, etc.

The scholar cites this example as an example: "In the epic, the adherence to and adherence to rhyme is so great that even the verses included in the middle of the rhyme are rhyming.", forty maidens took Barchin to the velvet house, brought clean clothes to this house, all boiled tea and sand, etc.”.

This is not poetry, but prose. But it is a rhyming prose, which in classical literature is called saj. So this method also has deep roots in folk poetry.

Thus, Maksud Shaikhzade studied works of folklore in comparison with classical literature. After all. the first basis of any word, image, artistic idea that has developed in the written literature is the oral creativity of the people. Maksud Shaikhzade understood this correctly and scientifically substantiated this situation in his articles.

Thus, Maksud Shaikhzade was able to contribute to the oral tradition of the people with his profound reflections on the epics "Sweet and Sugar", "Alpomish", "The path of creation of Bakhshi"

The second translation of Sheikhzade's tragedy was made in verse and was

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much better than the previous one. And also in 1960 [4, 384], due to the fact that at the same time a collection of Uzbek translations of Shakespeare's dramatic works was published, M. Sheikhzade revised and re-translated the tragedy with serious amendments. The Russian version of B. Pasternak was taken as a basis and in some places the translator used the Azerbaijani translation of Jabbar Jabbarali. The last translation was no longer close to the letter, but to the spirit of the original. The translator tried to get as close as possible to the original, explaining it, as if deciphering its content for the reader. The translator himself was a master of large-scale historical drama and philosophical lyrics.

Sheikhzade gave the greatest part of his creative energy to the works of W. Shakespeare. And this is no coincidence. The famous English artist John Dryden, defining Shakespeare's merits in the history of literature, emphasized that "Shakespeare was Homer or the father of our dramatic poets" [7, 4-1] He was also for Sheikhzade. Thanks to the independence of our Republic, significant changes are taking place in the field of literary translation, and direct translation is gaining more and more widespread use. In this direction, one cannot fail to note the enormous contribution of the greatest Uzbek national poet - translator Jamal Kamal. The Honored Art Worker of the Uzbek Republic made a great contribution to the formation and development of translation in Uzbekistan. His direct translations of Shakespeare's works made in 1991 [3,784]. year directly from English do not have a price. Jamal Kamal is a great, multifaceted artist, one of the founders of the Uzbek school of translation. Thanks to his translation activities, the Uzbek reader for the first time has the opportunity to get acquainted directly with the works of Shakespeare. J.

Kamal's appeal to Shakespeare is by no means a spontaneous phenomenon. J. Kamal did not immediately come to Shakespeare. This was preceded by years of persistent study of the work of the English playwright and the language of the translated work. Knowledge of the language in which the original being translated is written is not so much desirable as imperative. The translator read Shakespeare in the original, which created the necessary conditions for an authentic interpretation of the playwright's work. Shakespeare's tragedy "Hamlet", to which he looked closely back in the 70s and which literally "forced" to take up translation with its greatness of a poetic and philosophical mood. This happened in the 90s, when the translator felt the ripe potential in himself to cope with this particularly

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important task.

So in 1977 6 [8.1561 the first manuscript of the translation of the tragedy "Hamlet" appeared, which after 14 years, ie. in 1991 [3,784], it was reworked, which eloquently indicates the highly responsible attitude of J. Kamal to this immortal creation of Shakespeare.

And yet Sheikhzade's artistic conscience is clear before the Uzbek reader and the great English playwright: his translations are now read with unflagging interest. The "fault" of this is the original talent of the translator Sheikhzadeh, who managed to make the translations of Shakespeare's works in many ways worthy of the original even without knowing the English language. And not only this. Here, an important role was played by some immutable rules of Sheikhzade, which he never violates, which largely determines the quality of translations - a burning desire to recreate the characters and images of the original, the search for a linguistic equivalent, a principled attitude to the fact, to details, a plot phenomenon, compositional and semantic adequacy of the original.

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